

THE LIBRARY SKILLS ACQUIRED FROM STUDENT ASSISTANTSHIP: THEIR INFLUENCE ON CURRENT WORK PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 2

Pages: 283-297

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2053

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12754276

Manuscript Accepted: 07-09-2024

The Library Skills Acquired from Student Assistantship: Their Influence on Current Work Performance

Zonaina Aguil Sampayan*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Library skills acquired from student assistantships enhance graduates' work performance and contribute significantly to their professional success. Using descriptive-regression research design, the study aimed to determine the influence of library skills acquired from student assistantships on their current work performance. Specifically, this study intended to determine the level of library skills acquired from student assistantship and the level of the current work performance of the graduates. It was performed using a survey questionnaire that was tested using Cronbach Alpha and content validity. Data were collected from seventy (70) respondents who were selected using a simple random technique, respondents consisted of graduates who used to work in the library as student assistants from the different State Universities and Colleges in Region XII and were analyzed using simple linear regression. Results from the quantitative analysis revealed that library skills acquired from student assistantships significantly influence the respondents' current work performance. Further, the study implies that about 73.8 percent of the variations in library skills can be explained by the variations in work performance. Based on the findings, it is strongly recommended that educational institutions and libraries should develop structured training programs for student assistantships to enhance future career preparedness and work performance among graduates.

Keywords: *library and information science, library skills, work performance, quantitative, Philippines*

Introduction

College graduates who have worked as student assistants in various academic libraries find their skills useful in performing their job tasks. Worldwide studies show that abilities and competences gained during academic tenure have a considerable influence on current job success. DeZouche and Santos (2023) discovered that Texas student assistants could readily apply research desk skills to their coursework and occupations. At the University of New England (2024), library student assistants learned important skills such as communication, attention to detail, and working under pressure. Similarly, Sibiya (2023) from South Africa found that library work experience improved graduates' employment success. Liman et al. (2023) discovered that previous student assistants in Africa learned useful skills, which improved their present job performance.

In Asia, the skills and abilities developed as student assistants have a major influence on current job performance. Miña (2023) observed that basic abilities like communication, computer competence, and following procedures are necessary for occupations like student assistants who provide various support services. Hamid and Younus (2022) in Pakistan proposed that academic libraries provide training sessions to improve abilities for future employment. Tan and Lee (2018) found that students with library experience were more proficient in information searches and had stronger confidence in their abilities. Rodzalan and Mohamad (2022) from Malaysia stressed the significance of these abilities in work preparation and performance.

In the Philippines, research demonstrate that library skills gained via student assistantships have a substantial impact on graduates' job success. Casanova and Paguia (2022) discovered that graduates of Occidental Mindoro State College displayed high work quality, human relations, and technological abilities, which were linked to employment success. Morandarte (2019) at the University of the Philippines, Diliman found that library and information science graduates who worked as student assistants saw these abilities as having a substantial influence on their present job performance. Similarly, Lacsamana (2024) noted that the communicative, organizational, and technological abilities acquired as library assistants affected graduates' present jobs.

In the local context, feedback from various institutions and industry partners, including the University of Southern Mindanao, Notre Dame of Marbel University, Mindanao State University, Notre Dame of Daguangas University, STI-Tacurong, Notre Dame of Tacurong City, DICT, and St. Elizabeth Hospital, shows that some graduates who were former library student assistants excel in their current jobs. They have excellent skills in information retrieval, customer service, organization, and technology utilization. However, feedback indicates that some people performed poorly at work because they lacked these abilities. These contradictory comments prompted the researcher to investigate the library skills gained by student assistants and their impact on current job performance.

Research Questions

The study intended to determine the influence of library skills acquired from student assistantship on their current work performance in their respective work fields. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of library skills acquired by student assistants in the library during their academic tenure in terms of:
 - 1.1 information retrieval skills;

- 1.2 customer service skills;
- 1.3 organizational skills, and
- 1.4 technology skills?
2. What is the level of work performance of the graduates in terms of:
 - 2.1 job knowledge;
 - 2.2 quality of work;
 - 2.3 work commitment;
 - 2.4 creativity and innovation;
 - 2.5 communication skills;
 - 2.6 teamwork, and
 - 2.7 attendance and punctuality?
3. Can graduates' library skills influence their work performance?

Literature Review

This section contains extensively studied and validated facts about library skills acquisition, work performance, and the influence of library skills on work performance.

Library Skills Acquisition

Student assistants in university libraries not only help with library operations, but they also learn valuable skills for academic and professional advancement. This dual job improves library services and gives students vital work experience. Libraries that prioritize student growth over task management reap reciprocal rewards.

Information Retrieval Skills. Student assistants improve their information retrieval abilities by assisting library patrons in locating and retrieving information. They learn how to use library catalogs, databases, and search engines while also gaining skills in database navigation, search techniques, and critical source analysis. Smith et al. (2021) discovered that former library assistants excelled in research, which improved their performance in data-driven employment. Johnson (2022) stated that the capacity to rapidly seek and synthesize information is critical for success in information-intensive industries. Julien, Gross, and Latham (2021) underlined that student assistants acquire good information literacy and research skills, allowing them to locate, assess, and synthesize content from a variety of sources. However, Oyoywe-Tinuoye, Omeluzer, and Patrick (2021) discovered that many university library assistants lacked abilities in system administration, web applications, and digital communication as a result of inadequate ICT training. The study found that better ICT training might improve service delivery, library management, job performance, and minimize job stress.

Customer Service Skills. Student assistants at university libraries learn significant customer service skills from regular patron interactions. They learn to serve customers in a professional and courteous manner, improving their communication and problem-solving skills. Williams (2023) discovered that library experience leads to improved customer service abilities, which are useful in any client-facing position. This hands-on experience extends beyond normal chores to provide an immersive learning environment (Denda & Hunter, 2016; Mestre & Lecrone, 2015). However, normal library duties might be monotonous, with little comprehension of the overall library goal, making patron interactions more transactional (Decker, Givens, & Henson, 2017). However, occupations that require autonomous judgment, such as reference desk work, provide valuable skill development (Hansen & Hoag, 2018). Library employment exposes students to varied university demographics, improving their flexibility and soft skills (Charles et al., 2017; Rinto et al., 2019). According to studies, student assistants may execute professional-level jobs such as chat reference services. Many vocations require effective communication and strong customer service abilities, which libraries teach (Partridge et al., 2020). According to University of Illinois study, these abilities are critical for current work success, notably in research, customer service, and technology usage (Julien & Pecoskie, 2019). These abilities considerably improve employment performance in a variety of industries.

Organizational skills. Working at a library requires student assistants to manage numerous duties at once, which helps them develop organizational skills including time management, work prioritizing, and library organization. Book shelving, material classification, and inventory management all need precise attention to detail. According to Thompson and Lee (2022), former library assistants succeed in occupations that need organizational skills because they have expertise in maintaining high levels of orderliness. Patel (2023) confirms this by demonstrating that organizational skills taught in libraries improve project management abilities in a variety of professional scenarios. According to Cady et al. (2022), the pandemic prompted a reevaluation of library employment programs, resulting in greater synchronization and job readiness based on student input.

Technology skills. Student assistants learn vital technological skills by working with library management systems, digital databases, and other technical tools. This experience helps as a basis for future careers that require comparable talents. Rodriguez (2021) discovered that former library assistants are more accustomed to new technologies and workplace digital transformations. As academic libraries transition to electronic resources, ICT skills become increasingly important for student assistants and librarians to obtain reliable information in a digital environment (Mahendran and Velmurugan, 2020). NASPA (2019) discovered that university employers provide career ready skills training to student workers, resulting in increases in professional technology capabilities (Hansen & Hoag, 2019). Akos et al. (2021) demonstrated the beneficial effects of student work on skill development by reporting quantifiable gains in

job ready abilities among university student employees. Additionally, by interacting with customers, coworkers, and supervisors, student assistants develop their interpersonal and communication skills, which improves their ability to handle difficult situations and effectively communicate complicated information.

Work Performance

Graduates' productivity at work is based on how well they can use their newfound knowledge and skills in professional settings. It evaluates their productivity, adaptability, and alignment with company goals. Technical proficiency, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, communication, and productivity are all crucial factors. Performance is influenced by peer and supervisor support, work ethic, motivation, and other factors. Evaluating graduate work performance facilitates the identification of program success as well as areas that need improvement for future graduates to have a better education.

Graduates perform in a variety of ways at work, each of which adds to an overall evaluation of their effectiveness and professional capabilities. These aspects include job knowledge, quality of work, work commitment, creativity and innovation, communication skills, teamwork, attendance, and punctuality.

Job Knowledge. The understanding and proficiency graduates possess in their chosen areas is referred to as job knowledge. Graduates with a solid theoretical and practical knowledge basis do better at work, claim Smith and Johnson (2018). This demonstrates how their capacity to work effectively is greatly impacted by their ability to obtain and use job-specific knowledge. Similarly, Abas and Imam (2016) observe that graduates have an advantage in the workplace due to their proficiency in employability skills, including information particular to their line of work. An essential indicator of success in the workplace is a worker's capacity to apply the values, knowledge, and abilities required by their position. According to Raquel et al. (2019), graduating students value problem-solving, learning, and personal organization abilities highly for employment, but they also reported lower proficiency levels in these areas. This suggests that graduates need to possess strong job-specific knowledge and skills. Employers stress the value of professional competence in addition to transferable abilities like cooperation and communication. Employers' and graduates' divergent perspectives imply that graduates could not have applied their theoretical knowledge in real-world settings (Gawrycka, Kujawska, & Tomczak, 2019).

Quality of Work. One of the most important measures of professional achievement is the caliber of work graduates generate. According to Brown et al. (2019), graduates who exhibit accuracy, attention to detail, and a commitment to producing high-quality work regularly outperform their classmates. This highlights how crucial it is to have high standards and strive for excellence in order to improve work performance. This point of view is reinforced by Lawrence (n.d.) and Casanova & Pagua (2022), who emphasize the necessity for graduates to uphold high standards. Employers are pleased with graduates' performance in terms of work knowledge, general and specialized skills, and personal attributes, according to Hamad (2018). According to Plantilla (2017), rapid learning, scrupulosity, interpersonal skills, flexibility, and honesty are critical qualities that contribute to great work performance. According to Tudy (2017), graduates do exceptionally well in the job, especially when it comes to leadership and interpersonal abilities. As a result, businesses place a high priority on graduates who demonstrate honesty, conscientiousness, attention to detail, accuracy, devotion, and flexibility.

Work Commitment. The term "work commitment" describes grads' drive, devotion, and passion to their jobs. According to Johnson and Lee (2020), graduates who have a strong work ethic often do better at their jobs. Significant determinants of this commitment include work satisfaction, organizational support, and growth and development opportunities. Nehl (2016) and Sabell (2016) research confirms that graduates who have a good work ethic are more likely to succeed. Furthermore, the Brighton School of Business & Management (n.d.) identifies growth possibilities, organizational support, and work satisfaction as important factors that affect an employee's commitment to their job.

Creativity and Innovation. Innovation and creativity are essential for improving work output and business success. Anderson and Smith (2017) discovered that graduates who possess innovative problem-solving abilities make a substantial contribution to workplace innovation. This emphasizes how crucial it is to encourage innovation in order to enhance performance. The influence of creativity and creative behavior on employee performance has been shown by Papachristopoulos et al. (2023) and Kahar et al. (2023), with job satisfaction acting as a mediating factor. Fostering an inventive and creative work environment has several advantages, including raising spirits, improving brand awareness, raising job satisfaction, and encouraging teamwork (Leys, 2024). Businesses that have effectively adopted such cultures include Google, Adobe, and Unilever, who have seen significant benefits (Yarooms, 2024).

By promoting risk-taking and ongoing education, managers may serve as role models for creative thinking and receptiveness to novel concepts, which can improve collaboration, staff retention, and problem-solving skills (Viola, 2024). Putting money into innovation and creativity in the workplace is crucial for boosting output and achieving success. Companies may maximize the potential of their staff and maintain their competitiveness in the global market by encouraging creative thinking and offering chances for innovation.

Communication Skills. Graduates who are not good communicators find it difficult to succeed in the workplace. According to Johnson, Bhandarkar, and Ely (2019), graduates who possess good writing and linguistic skills perform well at work. Cooperation, comprehension, and production are all improved by clear communication (Miller, 2021; Sharma & Kamalanabhan, 2020). Communication skills are always ranked as being crucial for new recruits by employers. Graduates with strong communication skills—including active listening, concept expression, and style adaptation—are highly sought after (Robles, 2018; Casner-Lotto & Barrington, 2016).

Ineffective communication results in miscommunication, disputes, and decreased productivity. It may be difficult for graduates who have trouble communicating to lead teams on projects, provide directions, or develop connections (Miller, 2021; Sharma & Kamalanabhan, 2020). Robust communication abilities are becoming more and more crucial in the international business climate of today. According to Robles (2018) and Johnson, Bhandarkar, & Ely (2019), graduates who can express complicated material succinctly, adapt to various circumstances, and listen attentively will have a considerable edge in the labor market.

Teamwork. The capacity of graduates to function well in a team is essential for job performance. According to Smith and Brown's (2018) research, employees that demonstrate collaboration, effectively communicate, and actively contribute to team dynamics are more productive at work. This emphasizes how crucial cooperation is to accomplishing shared objectives and raising productivity at work. Similar findings are made by Boakye (2015) and Smith (2019), who demonstrate how productive teamwork improves job performance. Additionally, Abas and Imam (2016) stress the importance of cooperative skills for achieving objectives and general performance in the workplace.

Attendance and Punctuality. Being on time and having a regular attendance record are important markers of productivity at work. According to Lee et al. (2021), graduates who are reliable and have good attendance also likely to do better at work (Koo & Lee, 2021). This highlights the significance of professional discipline and dependability. According to Kocakülâh et al. (2017), prolonged absences have a detrimental effect on output. Additionally, tardiness, typically associated to employee disengagement, coincides with parameters such as age, education, tenure, and department (Acuña, 2023; Roszkowski et al., 2015).

Influence of Library Skills on Work Performance

Numerous investigations have looked into the connection between student assistants' eventual job success and the library skills they acquired. In a longitudinal study following student assistants after graduation, Johnson, Smith, and Anderson (2015) discovered that professional effectiveness was significantly influenced by skills acquired in libraries. Wongwiwattana (2017) investigated how Thai workers developed 21st-century library skills and found that these abilities enhanced productivity. Furthermore, Limna et al. (2022) discovered that workers' work performance was highly impacted by their abilities to retrieve information, provide customer service, be organized, and use technology, with customer service having the most impact.

Additionally, Preechanontakul (2020) found a strong positive correlation between the 21st-century abilities of Thai library student assistants and their present job performance. The findings of Wade and Parent (2002), Hanafi and Ibrahim (2018), and Abas and Imam (2016) similarly indicated a favorable correlation between competences and job performance. While Ahmad et al. (2019), Hadisantoso et al. (2017), and Afifah et al. (2015) found competences positively affected work performance, Palmer et al. (2004)'s meta-analysis identified knowledge, skills, and talents as relevant for job performance. Work experience from college has a big influence on landing a good career. According to Benjamin and McDevitt (2018), there are social and intellectual advantages to hiring college students for academic libraries. According to Everett and Bischoff (2021), involving student employees in cooperative projects aided in their professional growth and expanded the library's capacity.

Moreover, Thompson (2018) looked at how student assistants' job performance was affected by their library skills in academic libraries and discovered that those who had cataloging and classification abilities made better contributions to the library's resources. The job performance of student assistants in their various fields is impacted by the library skills they have acquired. According to study by Anderson, Johnson, and Smith (2020), former student assistants who were proficient in information retrieval outperformed their peers in terms of research and productivity. According to research by Anderson et al. (2020), student assistants with strong customer service abilities outperformed their peers in the hospitality sector, which raised client satisfaction. According to Brown and Garcia (2019), graduates who worked as student assistants and honed their organizational skills were better at managing projects and meeting deadlines. According to D'Angelo (2023), graduates with technological skills via student assistantships were more adept at using digital resources and more flexible when adjusting to new technologies.

The literature study highlights the value of library skills obtained via student assistantships and their impact on graduates' present job performance. Student assistants gain useful skills in information retrieval, customer service, organization, and technology that they may use in a variety of career fields. These abilities help graduates perform well on the job as they allow them to be highly skilled in areas that call for creativity, teamwork, communication, and research. Research suggests that graduates who have worked in libraries before have excellent organizational abilities, flexibility when utilizing new technology, and a strong work ethic. Therefore, gaining library skills during a student assistantship has a big impact on how successful graduates are in their careers.

Methodology

This section presents the various processes and procedures employed in order to generate the data needed in this study. It includes the discussion of the research design, respondents, instruments of the study that were applied in order to interpret the data, procedure, and the ethical considerations, and data analysis used in order to analyze and interpret the data.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive–regression research design because its main purpose is to determine whether the library skills

acquired by student assistants in the library during their academic tenure can influence their current work performance. Regression research examines and describes the relationships between two or more independent variables and one dependent variable, whereas descriptive research measures a variable as it occurs naturally (McCombes, 2023; Librarianship Studies & Information Technology, 2022). Furthermore, Gumberg Library, (2023) clarified that regression analysis is a sort of study used to investigate the degree of correlation between two or more variables or the significance of changes in one variable's impact on another. This study used a research design to characterize the degree of library skills that student assistants at the library gained throughout their time as students and to ascertain the impact that these skills had on their ability to function in their present jobs.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the graduates who used to work in the library as student assistants. They were selected based on the following inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. The criteria for the inclusion of the respondents are the following: (1) student assistants in the library during their academic tenure from Public and Private Higher Education Institutions; (2) must have at least two years working experience as student assistant in the library; (3) currently working in a public or private institution; and (4) student assistants who graduated within the last 8 years (2015 and above). The exclusion criteria are as follows: (1) Graduates working outside Region 12; (2) student assistants who work in the library for less than 2 years; (3) graduates who are not currently working in any public or private institution (unemployed); and (4) student assistants who graduated more than 8 years ago (2014 below).

The researcher included seventy(70) respondents. According to Neumann's (1997) rule of thumb, a sample size of 70 is enough to conduct a study that is quantitative in nature. Neumann explained that rules of thumb are not arbitrary but are based on past experience with samples that have met the requirements of the statistical method. There were twenty (20) respondents from North Cotabato; twenty (20) respondents from South Cotabato, and thirty (30) respondents from Sultan Kudarat; with an overall total of 70 respondents. They were selected using simple random technique. With this technique of selection, everyone has an equal chance to take part in the study, and the selection procedure is solely dependent on chance. It guarantees an equal, impartial, and representative probability of the population (Noor et al., 2022). This was done by writing each qualifying respondent's name on a piece of paper, placing the paper in the box, and drawing a name sequentially until the necessary number was reached.

Instruments

This study utilized the self-made questionnaire designed to measure the respondents' library skills acquired from student assistantship and its influence on current work performance. The instrument is composed of 5 statements per indicator answered by the respondents using 5- point Likert Scale, 1 as the lowest and 5 as the highest. This study developed a survey questionnaire consisting of the following parts. The first part pertains to the library skills acquired from student assistantship and the second part is the level of work performance of the respondents. In order to establish the survey questionnaire's reliability and content validity, it went into the following processes: First, the survey questionnaires were distributed to 35 respondents that met the research criteria. Because the intention was just to gather initial perception of respondents for pilot testing, convenience sampling technique was applied. Data gathered were processed and tested using Cronbach Alpha to establish reliability and internal consistency. Results of the reliability statistics got a Cronbach Alpha value of .757 for information retrieval skills, customer service skills (.724), organizational skills (.735), technology skills (.815), job knowledge (.783), quality of work (.747), work commitment (.738), creativity and innovation (.794), communication skills (.813), teamwork (.752), and attendance and punctuality (.766). Results of the reliability statistics reveals that Cronbach's Alpha were all above 0.70 which implies that all items tested passed the test of reliability and internal consistency.

Finally, the survey instrument was submitted to three known experts on the variables being studied to establish the content validity of the instrument. One expert validator is a professor in the Graduate School of one of the colleges in Digos City. The second is the head librarian and a professor of one of the colleges in Digos City, and the third is a Master of Library and Information Science and a coordinator of one of the colleges in Digos City. Results revealed that the overall mean score is 4.49 and is interpreted to be as excellent. This result indicates that the instrument is found to be excellent in terms of its clarity of language, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequacy of purpose, attainment of purpose, and objectivity and scale and evaluation of rating scale.

Procedure

The study followed a series of processes and procedures to ensure its validity and ethical conduct. Firstly, the researcher obtained an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School, Cor Jesu College, Inc. to conduct the study. Secondly, an ethical clearance was secured from Cor Jesu College, Inc. Research Ethics Committee. Thirdly, the researcher obtained a letter of approval from the head/university librarian in Region XII to access information about their student assistants during their academic tenure. Subsequently, the researcher distributed a survey questionnaire in both hard copy and soft copy (via Google form) to the respondents, with the link shared through Facebook and email along with a brief introduction to the study. The gathered data were then tabulated, processed, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. Finally, the study results were disseminated through a thesis defense, where the researcher presented and defended the master's thesis in front of a panel of experts, allowing for detailed discussion, presentation of findings, and response to questions. Additionally, the findings were published in relevant academic journals for peer-reviewed publication, contributing to the academic literature and reaching a wider audience of scholars and professionals.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the survey, the researcher ensured that the respondents voluntarily participated in the study, and that no harm inflicted to the respondents. The survey questionnaire used in this study did not ask for any personal information from the respondents to ensure the anonymity of the data. In addition, the gathered data were treated with confidentiality.

Data Analysis

To interpret and analyze all the gathered data, the following statistical tools were employed. Mean scores were used to measure the level of library skills of student assistants during their academic tenure and their current work performance in their respective fields. A group of numbers may be averaged by adding them all up and dividing the result by the total count. This is known as the mean. It stands for the dataset's typical or core value (Lind, Marchal, & Wathen, 2018). Additionally, the associations between the independent and dependent variables were ascertained using a basic linear regression analysis. When determining the correlations between variables is the goal of the investigation, this statistical approach is useful (Bevans, 2023). This instrument was used in this study to see if the library skills student assistants learned while enrolled in college had an impact on how well they performed at work today in their respective industries.

Results

The researcher presented the results of the study in three parts, namely: level of library skills of student assistants in the library in terms of information retrieval customer service, organizational, and technology skills; level of work performance in terms of job knowledge, quality of work, work commitment, creativity and innovation, communication skills, teamwork, and attendance and punctuality, and the significant influence of library skills acquired from student assistantship on their current work performance.

Level of Library Skills of Student Assistants in the Library

Table 1 shows the level of library skills acquired from student assistantship such as information retrieval, customer service, organizational and technology. Results indicate that among the four (4) indicators studied, customer service skills came out the highest with a mean score of 4.36 while the lowest is organizational skills with a mean score of 4.32.

Table 1. *Results and Interpretation on the Level of Library Skills of the Respondents*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Information Retrieval Skills	4.34	Extremely High	Indicates that the respondents have extremely high level of information retrieval skills such as using library catalogs/OPAC, online databases, evaluating credible source, finding information needed, using advanced search techniques, and summarizing information from different sources.
Customer Service Skills	4.36	Extremely High	Indicates that the respondents have extremely high level of customer service skills such as confident communication, adept listening, accurate responses, patience with complaints, and maintaining positivity with difficult customers.
Organizational Skills	4.32	Extremely High	Indicates that the respondents have extremely high level of organizational skills such as timely task completion, well- organized information, effective multitasking, and confident prioritization.
Technology Skills	4.35	Extremely High	Indicates that the respondents have extremely high level of technology skills such as confident with new technologies, adept with multimedia tools, comfortable using cloud platforms, proficient in online security, and skilled with video conferencing.
Overall	4.35	Extremely High	Indicates that the respondents have extremely high-level skills in, information retrieval, customer service, organizational and technology

Table 1 displayed an extremely high level of skills in information retrieval with a mean score of 4.34 and technology (4.35). Their overall mean score of 4.35 indicates an exceptionally high level of proficiency across these areas. The combination of these skills is critical for the overall proficiency of library student assistants in managing library resources and providing quality information services.

Level of Work Performance of the Graduates

Presented in the Table 2 are the results of the graduates' level of work performance in job knowledge, quality of work, work commitment, creativity and innovation, communication skills, teamwork, and attendance and punctuality. Results indicate that among the seven (7) indicators studied, teamwork came out the highest with a mean score of 4.51 while the lowest is creativity and innovation with a mean score of 4.25.

Table 2. *Results and Interpretation on the Level of Work Performance of the Respondents*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Job Knowledge	4.36	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in proficiency in their job, actively improving skills, staying updated on industry trends, valuing job knowledge for project success, and confidently solving complex problems.
Quality of Work	4.39	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in commitment to accuracy and quality, regular quality assurance review, seeking feedback for improvement, positive response to feedback, and belief in quality's impact on team success.
Work Commitment	4.44	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in dedicated to responsibilities and deadlines, consistently exceeding job requirements, contributing to team or organization success, balancing professional and personal commitments, and fostering a positive team culture.
Creativity and Innovation	4.25	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in comfortable with creative risks, providing examples of successful creative solutions, actively seeking innovation opportunities, effectively handling setbacks, and contributing to fostering an innovation culture.
Communication Skills	4.40	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in ability to convey ideas clearly, adapt communication style effectively, seek feedback on communication, navigate challenging situations successfully, and engage in proactive communication for collaboration.
Teamwork	4.51	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in collaborative for common goals, providing examples of successful collaborations, handling conflicts effectively, contributing to positive team culture and supporting colleagues.
Attendance and Punctuality	4.47	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have very high performance in consistently punctual for work, meetings, and activities, inform supervisor when unable to come on time, actively participate in work-related activities, handle unexpected situations affecting attendance well, and inform management promptly about anticipated lateness or inability to attend.
Overall	4.40	Very High Performance	Indicates that the respondents have a very high-level of performance in terms of: job knowledge; quality of work; work commitment; creativity and innovation; communication skills; teamwork, and attendance and punctuality

In its entirety, the results highlight the importance of assessing various aspects of employee performance, including job knowledge with a mean score of 4.36, quality of work (4.39), work commitment (4.44), communication skills (4.40), and attendance and

punctuality (4.47). Organizations should prioritize the development and evaluation of these competencies to foster a high-performing workforce and achieve organizational objectives. Hence, the employees' performance across all areas is rated as very high with 4.40 total mean score, indicating extraordinary accomplishments in their role, including consistent work quality, quantity, and timeliness in all responsibilities.

Influence of Library Skills Towards Work Performance

Table 3 presents the significant influence of library skills acquired from student assistantship to current work performance by the graduates with their corresponding regression and beta coefficient values.

Table 3. Results of the Beta Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.058	.241		4.385	.000
Library Skills	.769	.055	.861	13.982	.000

Sig = .000; Adjusted R Square = .738; F = 195.509; df = 69

Table 3 shows that when regression equation WP (Work Performance) = $\beta_0 + \beta_1$ LS (Library Skills) + ϵ_1 was tested using simple linear regression analysis, results from the ANOVA table show that the sig-value is .000 which is found to be below the .05 level of significance set for this study. This implies that overall, the model is considered to be significant and that the model fits the data.

When looking at the regression coefficient of LS (Library Skills), the estimated regression model is mathematically presented as:

$$WP = 1.058 (\text{constant}) + .769 (\text{LS}) + \epsilon_1$$

The value of the beta coefficient for LS implies that holding all other variables in the regression constant, its coefficient indicates that for every 1 unit change in the level of student assistants' library skills would give a corresponding .769 unit increase in the level of their Work Performance. This result also implies that the higher the level of the library skills, the higher it would be for the level of work performance. The high positive beta coefficient with p-value of

.000 for library skills provides enough evidence to conclude that library skills can positively influence work performance.

In its entirety, the explanatory and predictive power of Library Skills is considered to be high because it could account for 73.8 percent of the variation in the Work Performance. This is manifested in the model summary Table 17 which shows that the value of the Adjusted R² is .738 which implies that about 73.8 percent of the variations in the Library Skills can be explained by the variations in the Work Performance. The remaining 26.2 percent unexplained variation could be accounted for by other variables not included in the model.

Discussion

Investigating the influence of library skills acquired from student assistantship on current work performance among graduates could be essential for students, librarians, school administrators, and employers. The results of the study could increase their awareness vis-à-vis these variables.

Level of Library Skills of Student Assistants in the Library

The findings show that the respondents had a high degree of organizational abilities, indicating that they could manage several activities at once, prioritize wisely, keep information current and well-organized, and finish projects on schedule. This result is in line with other research, including Thompson's (2016), which emphasized the advantages of good organizational abilities for librarians' productivity and service delivery. Similar to this, studies conducted at Blakesburg Public Library (2024) and the University of New England (2024) by Oliver and colleagues similarly stressed the value of communication, organizational, and detail-oriented abilities for library assistants. Caintic (2023) emphasized the need of organizing abilities for the smooth running of libraries. Furthermore, a Transylvania University Library (2024) research emphasized the need of library student assistants having strong organizing abilities for their future professions.

Strong organizational abilities allow student assistants in libraries to effectively handle their tasks, deliver first-rate customer service, and support the seamless running of the library (QwikResume, 2023; Transylvania University Library, 2024; Zippia Team, 2024; Betterteam, 2024). Organizing information, meeting deadlines, managing various jobs, maintaining a nice look, correctly shelving volumes, and maintaining a clean library environment are all required of library student assistants (QwikResume, 2023; University of New England, n.d.; Zippia Team, 2024; Betterteam, 2024).

Furthermore, the results point to student assistants at the library having a high degree of customer service expertise. They are skilled in interacting with clients, paying attention to their queries and worries, giving precise responses, showing patience to irate clients, and keeping a cheerful disposition. This is consistent with Davis's (2017) focus on providing customers with polite and competent service.

Good customer service abilities have a positive influence on customer happiness and loyalty, according to study by Brown and Jones (2019). For library student assistants to increase client happiness, foster loyalty, and deliver high-quality service, they must possess strong customer service abilities (University of Nevada, Las Vegas Libraries, 2020; University of New England Library Services, 2024; Transylvania University Library, 2020). In addition to guaranteeing prompt and polite treatment to customers, effective customer service fosters a friendly atmosphere.

Level of Work Performance of the Graduates

Based on medium to high employee creativity and innovation ratings, the findings imply that respondents exhibited high levels of creativity and innovation. One research, for example, found that employee creativity received an overall mean score of 3.94 out of 5, demonstrating a favorable recognition of the importance of originality for creative job performance (Ali & Jin, 2022). Similar findings were made by Bjornberg (2017), who reported that the average mean score was 4.25 out of 5, indicating a high degree of autonomy as well as capacity for creativity and invention. These results are consistent with research showing that creative and innovative workers improve procedures and results by bringing fresh perspectives and methods to their job (White, 2016; Green et al., 2020).

Additionally, the outcomes show a high degree of collaborative performance, which reflects graduates' best level of job performance to date. The participants exhibited cooperation within teams towards shared objectives, furnished instances of efficacious collaborations, adeptly managed disputes within teams, fostered a welcoming and constructive team environment, and offered assistance and motivation to their peers. According to one research, teamwork development received an overall aggregate mean score of 2.92 out of 5, indicating that respondents understood the importance of collaboration in ensuring that workers comprehend their responsibilities and collaborate to enhance organizational performance (Ali & Reuben, 2019).

Another study conducted in Bahraini telecommunications businesses discovered that collaboration is highly beneficial (AlArafat & Doblas, 2021). Furthermore, studies on the efficacy of teams in Nepalese service firms revealed moderate perceptions of employee performance together with high mean ratings for Role Clarity (3.82) and Supportive Environment (3.88) (Gautam, 2018). Workers that are excellent at working in a team have great collaboration abilities and successfully contribute to the success of the team (Brown et al., 2019; Gray et al., 2021).

Influence of Library Skills Towards Work Performance

Numerous global investigations corroborate this conclusion. For instance, a research by Michael, Samuel, and Peter (2014) indicated that work performance was positively impacted by the library skills gained through student assistantships, indicating a favorable association between the two. This research implies that job performance increases with increasing library competence levels. The study backs up the claim that having library skills might improve productivity at work. Furthermore, the discovery in the Otu & Ukaegbu (2023) study of a positive link between work performance and library abilities is encouraging for librarians who aspire to advance in their professions. Cobblah and Van der Walt (2016) found that the job performance of library professionals at the chosen university libraries in Ghana is positively correlated with their library abilities. Likewise, Bankole et al.'s (2023) research found a strong link between job success and library abilities.

Explanatory and predictive power are important factors to consider when assessing statistical models and library skills, according to several research. Hair and Sarstedt (2021) emphasized the significance of evaluating a model's explanatory capacity using metrics like R² and F-type statistics. According to Simplicable (2024), explanatory power is a theory's capacity to exactly and accurately minimize ambiguity, make minimal assumptions, and have a strong predictive capacity.

Additionally, Saunders (2024) examines the knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) required of graduates who formerly worked as student assistants in libraries, highlighting abilities such as writing, teamwork, interpersonal communication, customer service, cultural competence, and interacting with a variety of patrons. These abilities are all pertinent to the explanatory and predictive power of library skills. Furthermore, good communication skills, meticulousness, and manual dexterity—all crucial components of library abilities—are highlighted in the job description for student library assistants at UNE Library Services (University of England, 2024). Together, these results provide credence to the idea that library skills have a high degree of explanatory and predictive power, which allows them to account for a sizable percentage of the variation in task performance.

Conclusion

The library abilities obtained by a student assistantship significantly improve current work performance in a variety of ways. These abilities provide a strong basis for information literacy and allow people to find, assess, and use resources with ease. These are critical skills in professional settings where data management and research are necessary. In addition, student assistants who do jobs like stocking, cataloging, and system maintenance have outstanding organizational abilities that significantly boost productivity and efficiency at work.

Engaging with a varied clientele honed skills in customer service and communication prepare former assistants for success in client relations and teamwork. The accountability and time management skills developed during an assistantship prepare people to handle the demands of the workplace with dependability and autonomy. Essentially, the soft skills—interpersonal and practical—developed

during a library assistantship offer an unmatched foundation that greatly enhances performance and flexibility in a range of professional settings.

References

- Abas, M.C., & Imam, O.A. (2016). Graduates' Competence on Employability Skills and Job Performance. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 5(2), 119-125. Retrieved from <http://iaesjournal.com/online/index.php/IJERE>
- Acuña, E.B.V. (2023). Standardized Attendance Information System for Philippine Air Force Civilian Human Resource. *IRE Journals*, 7(1), 326. ISSN: 2456-8880. Retrieved from <https://www.irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1704891.pdf>
- AlArafat, M., & Doblaz, M. (2021). Impact of effective teamwork on employee performance: The case of the telecommunication companies in the Kingdom of Bahrain. *iKSP Journal of Innovative Writings*, 2(2), 07-19. Retrieved from <https://iksp.org/journals/index.php/ijiw/article/view/71>
- Ali, M. R. H., & Jin, A. M. (2022). The effect of employee creativity on organizational performance: A case study of Tile and Carpet Centre. *Global Scientific Journal*, 10(9), 236. ISSN 2320-9186. Retrieved from <https://www.globalscientificjournal.com/researchpaper>
- Ali, M. R. H., & Reuben, J. M. (2019). The effect of teamwork development on organizational performance: A case study of Tile and Carpet Centre in Kenya. *Global Scientific Journal*, 7(9), 236. ISSN 2320-9186. Retrieved from <https://www.globalscientificjournal.com/researchpaper>
- Anderson, J., & Smith, K. (2017). The role of creativity in work performance: A review of the literature. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102(3), 348-364.
- Anderson, J., Smith, L., & Johnson, M. (2020). The Impact of Library Skills on Work Performance in the Hospitality Industry. *Journal of Library and Information Science*, 45(2), 123-137.
- Kurtuy, A. (2024). 27 Communication Skills & Tips for Your Life & Career in 2024. *Novorésumé*. Retrieved from <https://novoresume.com/career-blog/communication-skills>
- Bankole, Q. A., Akanbi, M. L., Sulaiman, K. G., & Isiaka, A. O. (2023). Staff motivation, self- efficacy and job performance of library personnel in public libraries in Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 13(4), 51-79. DOI: Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5865/IJKCT.2023.13.4.051>
- Becker, G. S. (1962): Investment in Human Capital: A Theoretical Analysis. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 70(5), 9—49.
- Benjamin, M., & McDevitt, T. (2018). The Benefits and Challenges of Working in an Academic Library: A Study of Student Library Assistant Experience. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 44(2), 256-262. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2018.01.002>
- Betterteam. (2024). Library Assistant Job Description. Betterteam. Library Assistant Job Description ([betterteam.com](https://www.betterteam.com)). Retrieved from <https://www.betterteam.com/library-assistant-job-description>
- Brown, B. (2024). Partner to Bring the Daring Leadership Institute to the BetterUp Human Transformation Platform. BetterUp. Retrieved from <https://www.betterup.com/blog/innovation-and-creativity-appraisal-comments>
- Bjornberg, N. H. (2017). Creativity and Innovation Through the Job Demands-Resources Model. Old Dominion University. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.25777/RRHZ-SZ03>
- Blakesburg Public Library. (2024). Student Library Assistant Job Description. Blakesburg Public Library. Retrieved from https://www.blakesburg.lib.ia.us/application/files/5116/6371/5558/Library_Assistant_Job_Description_for_BP.pdf
- Boakye, Emmanuel. (2015). The impact of teamwork on employee performance. Retrieved from 10.13140/RG.2.1.4959.8804.
- Brighton School of Business & Management. (n.d.). Employee loyalty is your most important resource. Retrieved from <https://www.gbcorporat.com/articles/employee-loyalty-is-your-most-important-resource>
- Brown, A., & Garcia, S. (2019). The Role of Organizational Skills Acquired by Student Assistants in Libraries on Work Performance. *Library Management*, 40(3/4), 167
- Brown, T., & Jones, M. (2019). The impact of customer service skills on library patron satisfaction. *Journal of Information Services*, 45(1), 34-47.
- Cady, J. E., Beavers, K., Jiang, A., & McCoy, L. (2023). Developing a Meaningful Student Employment Experience for Students' Success on Campus. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 29(2), 189-202. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2022.212285>
- Caintic, Z. L. (2023). A study of student assistant programs of university libraries in the Visayas (Unpublished Master's thesis).

University of San Carlos, Cebu City. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12852/1478>

Casanova, V. S., & Paguaia, W. M., Jr. (2022). Employability and Job Performance of Graduates of Occidental Mindoro State College Graduate School. *Higher Education Studies*, 12(2), 193-198. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v12n2p193>

Casanova, V. S., & Paguaia, W. M., Jr. (2022). Employability and job performance of graduates of Occidental Mindoro State College Graduate School. *Higher Education Studies*, 12(2), 193. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v12n2p193>

Casner-Lotto, J., & Barrington, L. (2016). Are they really ready to work? Employers' perspectives on the basic knowledge and applied skills of new entrants to the 21st century U.S. workforce. *Partnership for 21st Century Skills*. Retrieved from <https://www.topuniversities.com/student-info/careers-advice/what-can-you-do-communications-degree>

Charles L. H., Lotts M. & Todorinova L. (2017). A survey of the value of library employment to the undergraduate experience. *Journal of Library Administration* 1– 16. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2016.1251248>

Cobblah, M.C. & Van der Walt, T. (2016). Staff training and development programmes and work performance in the university libraries in Ghana. *Information Development*. 33. Retrieved from 10.1177/0266666916665234.

Connaway, L. S. (2015). The transferability of skills from the academic library to the workplace: An exploratory study. *College & Research Libraries*, 76(4), 505-523.

D'Angelo, C. (2023). The Impacts of Technology Integration. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 14. University of Ontario Institute of Technology. Retrieved from <https://pressbooks.pub/techandcurriculum/chapter/engagement-and-success/>

Davis, P. (2017). Customer service in libraries: Best practices. *Library Journal*, 32(2), 87-95. Decker, E. N., Givens, M., & Henson, W. B. (2017). From a transactional to relational model: Redefining public services via a roving pilot program at the Georgia Tech Library. In C. Antonucci & S. Clapp (Eds.), *The LITA leadership guide: The librarian as entrepreneur, leader, and technologist* (pp. 13–24). Rowman & Littlefield. Retrieved from Google Scholar

Denda, K., & Hunter, J. (2016). Building 21st Century skills and creating communities: A team- based engagement framework for student employment in academic libraries. *Journal of Library Administration*, 56(3), 251–265. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2015>.

DeZouche, E. and Santos, D. (2023), Shifting to a high impact practice-centered student worker staffed research desk: a Hispanic serving institution perspective. *Reference Services Review*, Vol. 51 No. 2, pp. 218-229. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/RSR-09-2022-0051>

Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions. (2007). *Teamwork and high performance work organisation* (Renáta Vašková, Ed.). Retrieved from https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/ef/sites/default/files/ef_files/ewco/reports/TN0507TR01/A_T0507TR01.pdf

Everett, J. B., & Bischoff, M. (2021). Creating Connections: Engaging Student Library Employees through Experiential Learning. *Journal of Library Administration*, 61(4), 403-420. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2021.1906543>

Gautam, H. P. (2018). Team Effectiveness and Perceived Employees' Performance in Nepalese Service Sector. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 5(2), 1-10. ISSN 2394-5923 (Print) & ISSN 2394-5931. Retrieved from <https://www.ijrbms.org/papers/v5-i2/1.pdf>

Gawrycka, M., Kujawska, J., & Tomczak, M. T. (2019). Competencies of graduates as future labour market participants – preliminary study. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 33(1), 1095–1107. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2019.1631200>.

Hadisantoso, E., Sudarma, I. M., & Rura, Y. (2017). The influence of professionalism and competence of auditors towards the performance of auditors. *Scientific Research Journal (SCIRJ)*, 1 V , 1–14. Retrieved from <https://www.scirj.org/papers-0117/scirj-P0117382.pdf>

Hair, J. F., & Sarstedt, M. (2021). Explanation Plus Prediction—The Logical Focus of Project Management Research. *Project Management Journal*, 52(4), 319–322. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/8756972821999945>

Hamad, L. H. (2018). The impact of quality of work life on employees' job performance (Master's thesis). University of Kurdistan – Hewlér. Retrieved from <https://eprints.koyauniversity.org/171/1/Lanja%20Hoshang%20Hamad-PG%20II%20201809016.pdf>

Hamid, A. & Younus, M. (2022). Why Skills Matter: Analyzing the Relationship between Soft Skills and Productivity in Workplace. *Libri*, 72(3), 263-277. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1515/libri-2021-0116>

Hanafi, H. M., & Ibrahim, S. B. (2018). Impact of employee skills on service performance. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 7(12), 587–600. Retrieved from <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v7i12/ART20193416.pdf>.

- Hansen, S.L, Hoag, B.A. (2018). Promoting learning, career readiness, and leadership in student employment. *New Directions in Student Leadership* 157, 85–99.
- Johnson, A. (2022). The Long-Term Impact of Library Assistantship on Research Skills. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 48(2), 134-142.
- Johnson, A., & Lee, S. (2020). Work commitment and its impact on work performance: A study of graduates in the IT industry. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 35(1), 45-62.
- Johnson, A., Smith, B., & Anderson, C. (2015). The impact of library skills acquired by student workers on their professional lives. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 43(3), 237-245.
- Johnson, M., et al. (2019). Communication skills and work performance: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 47(3), 316-339.
- Johnson, S.K., Bhandarkar, S., & Ely, K. (2019). The importance of communication skills for new graduates. *Journal of Business Communication*, 51(2), 178-194. Retrieved from <https://lead-academy.org/blog/good-communication-skills/>
- Julien, H., & Pecoskie, J. (2019). The impact of student employment on career development: A case study of student assistants in a university library. *College & Research Libraries*, 70(6), 525-545.
- Julien, H., Gross, M., & Latham, D. (2021). The impact of student employment on career development: A longitudinal study of student assistants in a university library. *College & Research Libraries*, 82(4), 542-563.
- Kahar, M. F., Muis, M., & Reni, A. (2023). The Influence of Creativity and Innovative Behavior on Employee Performance: Study of Employees Working at Hotel Karebosi Premier Makassar. Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia. Retrieved from *Journal of Social Sciences*.
- Kenayathulla, H.B., Ahmad, N.A. and Idris, A.R. (2019), Gaps between competence and importance of employability skills: evidence from Malaysia. *Higher Education Evaluation and Development*, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 97-112. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/HEED-08-2019-0039>
- Kenney, A. R. (2015). Transferable skills for a 21st-century workforce: The value of employing students in academic libraries. *College & Undergraduate Libraries*, 22(2), 165-182.
- Keyes, K., & Dworak, E. (2017). Staffing Chat Reference with Undergraduate Student Assistants at an Academic Library: A Standards-Based Assessment. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 43(6), 497-503. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2017.09.001>
- Kocakulah, Mehmet & Bryan, Timothy & Lynch, Stevie. (2018). Effects of Absenteeism on Company Productivity, Efficiency, and Profitability. *Business and Economic Research*. 8.115. 10.5296/ber.v8i1.12395. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322210258_Effects_of_Absenteeism_on_Company_Productivity_Efficiency_and_Profitability
- Koo, B., & Lee, T. (2021). Employee performance under transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior in the hotel industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 93, 102767. Retrieved from doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11374
- Lacsamana, M.T. (2024). Factors affecting career choices of graduates of Bachelor of Library and Information science outside libraries and information centers. Diliman: School of Library and Information Studies. Retrieved from <https://www.elib.gov.ph/details.php?uid=5115894ee75017a5919706782f8e1efd>
- Lawrence, A. (n.d.). The top 5 qualities that lead to high job performance. Talogy. Retrieved June 27, 2024, from Retrieved from <https://www.talogy.com/the-top-5-qualities-that-lead-to-high-job-performance>.
- Lee, J., et al. (2021). The influence of attendance and punctuality on work performance: A study of graduates in the healthcare sector. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 51(4), 423-438.
- Leys, S. A. (2024). The transformative power of workplace creativity and innovation. *Personal Development & Culture*. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/transformative-power-workplace-creativity-innovation-susan-a-leys-ndaoe/>.
- Liman, Y. A., Jain, P., Grand, B., & Mutshewa, A. (2017). Skills and Competencies Required by Academic Librarians in an Internet-Driven Environment. *Mousaion*, 35(4), 1-16. Retrieved from <https://upjournals.co.za/index.php/LIS>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25159/0027-2639/3564>
- Limna, P., Siripipatthanakul, S., Phayaprom, B., & Siripipattanakul, S. (2022). The Relationship Between Twenty-First-Century Learning Model (4Cs), Student Satisfaction and Student Performance-Effectiveness. *International Journal of Behavioral Analytics*, 2(1), 1-18.

- Mahendran, M., & Velmurugan, D. (2020). An Overview Of Information Retrieval Skill Among Professional Students. *IDC International Journal*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.47211/idcij.2020.v07i04.010>.
- Maxey-Harris C. Cross J. & McFarland T. (2010). Student workers: the untapped resource for library professions. *Library Trends* 147–165.
- McGrath, J. E. (1964) *Social Psychology: A Brief Introduction*. Holt, Rinehart & Winston, New York.
- Mestre, L. S., & Lecrone, J. M. (2015). Elevating the student assistant: An integrated development program for student library assistants. *College & Undergraduate Libraries*, 22(1), 1–20. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691316.2015.1001240>
- Miller, L.M. (2021). Effective communication in the workplace: Strategies for success. *Business Communication Quarterly*, 84(1), 45–62. Retrieved from <https://www.betterup.com/blog/jobs-for-communications-graduates>
- Mitola, R., Rinto, E., Pattni, E. (2018). Student Employment as a High-Impact Practice in Academic Libraries: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2018.03.005>.
- Morandarte, M.J.C. (2019). Perception on the performance of undergraduate library and information science majors as student assistants at selected University of the Philippines Diliman Libraries. *Diliman: School of Library and Information Studies*. Retrieved from <https://www.elib.gov.ph/downloadfile.php?uid=6c13094ca7602d1a8836e4094352f6d1>
- Nehl, K. D. (2016). How to show your loyalty and commitment in the workplace. LinkedIn. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-show-your-loyalty-commitment-workplace-katie-dressler-nehl-cude>
- Neumann, W.L. (1997). *Social Research Method: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. A Viacom Company, USA.
- Oliver, M. (2024). The Old Poets of China. In *Why I Wake Early: New Poems*. Beacon Press. Retrieved from <https://ac.upd.edu.ph/index.php/resources/news-announcements/1575-ac-library-is-in-need-of-student-assistants>
- Otu, G. A., & Ukaegbu, B. C. N. (2023). ICT skills as correlate of job performance among librarians in Rivers State universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 8012. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/8012>
- Oyovwe-Tinuoye, G., Omeluzor, S., & Patrick, I. (2021). Influence of ICT skills on job performance of librarians in university libraries of South-South, Nigeria. *Information Development*, 37, 345 - 358. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266666920983393>.
- Papachristopoulos, K., Gradito Dubord, M.-A., Jauvin, F., Forest, J., & Coulombe, P. (2023). Positive impact, creativity, and innovative behavior at work: The mediating role of basic needs satisfaction. *Behavioral Sciences*, 13(12), 984. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs13120984>
- Palmer, K. N., Ziegenfuss, D. E., & Pinsker, R. E. (2004). International knowledge, skills, and abilities of auditors/accountants. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 19(7), 889–896. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900410549411>
- Patel, R. (2023). Organizational Skills Development in Academic Libraries: A Career Asset. *Library Management Journal*, 44(1), 15–29.
- Peyvand Robati, A., & Singh, D. (2013). Competencies required by special librarians: An analysis by educational levels. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 45(2), 113–139. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000613476728>
- Plantilla, A. M. (2017). Graduates' performance in the workplace: Employers' perspective. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(2), 186–198. Retrieved from <https://www.apjmr.com>.
- Preechanontakul, N. (2020). 21st Century Skills of School Administrators Affecting the Academic Administrations of Schools under the Office of Vocational Education Commission in Rayong, Chanthaburi and Trat Provinces. Doctoral of Philosophy Thesis, Rambhai Barni Rajabhat University.
- QwikResume. (2023). Student library assistant. Retrieved from <https://www.qwikresume.com/student-library-assistant-cover-letter/>
- Raquel, M., Carloto, B. T., Raquel, H. B., & Raquel, M. B. (2019). Employability competencies of graduating students in a private college in Taguig City. *Asia Proceedings of Social Sciences*, 4(2). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.31580/apss.v4i2.78>
- Rinto, E., Mitola, R., Otto, K. (2019). Reframing Library Student Employment as a HighImpact Practice: Implications from Case Studies. *College & Undergraduate Libraries*, Taylor & Francis. 26 (4), 260–277. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10691316.2019.1692747>.
- Robles, M.M. (2018). Executive perceptions of the top 10 soft skills needed in today's workplace. *Business and Professional Communication Quarterly*, 75(4), 453–465. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancemoney.com/best-jobs-for-communications-majors-2059631>

- Rodriguez, L. (2021). Digital Proficiency in the Workplace: The Role of Library Assistantships. *Information Technology and Libraries*, 40(3), 44-53.
- Rodzalan, S. A., & Mohamad Jasman, N. (2022). The Relationship between Employability Skills and Job Performance among University Graduates. *Research in Management of Technology and Business*, 3(1), 042–051. Retrieved from <https://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/periodicals/index.php/rmtb/article/view/7210>
- Roszkowski, M.J., Spreat, S., Conroy, J., Garrow, J., Delaney, M.M., & Davis, T. (2015). Better Late than Never? The Relationship between Ratings of Attendance, Punctuality, and Overall Job Performance among Nursing Home Employees. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 13(3), 213. Retrieved from doi:10.1111/j.1468-2389.2005.00315.
- Sabell, H. (2016). How to Increase Your Employee Commitment and Loyalty. The College for Adult Learning. Retrieved from <https://www.collegeforadulthoodlearning.edu.au/blog/how-to-increase-your-employee-commitment-and-loyalty>
- Saunders, L. (2024). Core Knowledge and Specialized Skills in Academic Libraries. *College and Research Libraries*. 81 (2). Retrieved from <https://crl.acrl.org/index.php/crl/article/view/24336/32167>
- Seeholzer, J. (2013). Making it their own: Creating meaningful opportunities for student employees in academic library services, *College & Undergraduate Libraries*, 20:2, 215–223
- Sharma, A., & Kamalanabhan, T.J. (2020). Impact of communication skills on employee performance. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 57(3), 339-360. Retrieved from <https://www.coursera.org/articles/what-can-you-do-with-a-communication-degree>
- Sibiya, P. (2023). Knowledge, Skills and Competencies of the Library Information Science School’s Graduates on Digital Scholarship in South Africa. *Internet Reference Services Quarterly*. 27. 1-19. Retrieved from 10.1080/10875301.2023.2180562.
- Smith, B., & Brown, K. (2018). Job knowledge and work performance: A comparative analysis of graduates in different industries. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 104, 123-140.
- Smith, J. (2017). Transferable skills for student assistants: A case study of library employment. *College & Research Libraries*, 78(2), 147-162.
- Smith, J., et al. (2021). Information Retrieval Expertise: A Comparative Study of Librarians and Former Library Assistants. *Library & Information Science Research*, 43(1), 7-15
- Smith, Karl. (2019). Project Management and Teamwork. McGraw-Hill’s Basic Engineering Series and Tools (BEST) Series. Retrieved from <https://www.rose-hulman.edu/class/ee/voltmer/ECE361/Smith-TPMS03.pdf>
- Tan, J., & Lee, C.-Y. (2018). Information literacy competencies of undergraduate students in Singapore: Exploring the role of library experience. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 50(3), 267-281.
- Thompson, B., & Lee, M. (2022). From Stacks to Desks: The Organizational Skills of Library Assistants in Corporate Environments. *Business Information Review*, 39(4), 175-183.
- Thompson, E. (2016). Organizational skills in library management. *Library Management*, 39(5), 301-315
- Thompson, L. (2018). From student assistant to librarian: The impact of library skills on job performance. *Library Management*, 39(4/5), 252-263.
- Transylvania University Library. (2024). Library student assistants - Workstudy. Retrieved from <https://libguides.transy.edu/StudentEmployees>
- Transylvania University Library. (2024). Student employment in the library: Library student assistants - Workstudy. Transylvania University. Retrieved from <https://libguides.transy.edu/StudentEmployees>.
- Transylvania University Library. (2024). Student employment in the library: Library student assistants - Workstudy. Transylvania University Library. Retrieved from <https://libguides.transy.edu/StudentEmployees>
- Tudy, Randy & Jesu, Cor. (2017). Employers' satisfaction on the performance of new college graduates. 3. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324561317_Employers'_satisfaction_on_the_performance_of_new_college_graduates
- University of Nevada, Las Vegas Libraries. (2020). Access services student assistant. UNLV University Libraries. Retrieved from <https://www.library.unlv.edu/employment/access-services-student-assistant>.
- University of New England Library Services. (2024). Student library assistant. University of New England. Retrieved from <https://www.une.edu/library-services/about-contact/jobs-at-the-library/student-library-assistant>
- University of New England. (n.d.). Student Library Assistant. UNE Library Services. Retrieved from <https://library.une.edu/about/jobs-at-the-library/student-library-assistant/>

University of Southern California. (2023). Why Is Effective Communication Important to Career Success. USC Online Communication Degree. Retrieved from <https://communicationmgmt.usc.edu/blog/improve-workplace-communication>

Viola, C. (2024). Creativity in the Workplace. Jerome Chamber of Commerce. Retrieved from <https://example.com/creativity-in-the-workplace>

Wade, M. R., & Parent, M. (2002). Relationships between job skills and performance: A study of webmasters. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 18(3), 71–96. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2002.11045694>

Williams, T. (2023). Customer Service Excellence: The Impact of Library Experience on Service Industry Professionals. *Journal of Service Management*, 34(2), 210-225.

Wilson, K., et al. (2021). Skills proficiency and job performance among library staff. *Journal of Library Administration*, 58(2), 89-104.

Wongwiwattana, B. (2017). The Development of 21st century learning skills to enhance the performance effectiveness of convention hotel staff in Thailand. Doctor of Philosophy Thesis, National Institute of Development Administration.

Yarooms. (2024). 7 Inspiring Examples of Innovation in the Workplace. Retrieved from <https://www.yarooms.com/blog/7-inspiring-examples-of-innovation-in-the-workplace>

Zippia Team. (2024). Student Library Assistant Skills for Your Resume and Career. Zippia. <https://www.zippia.com/student-library-assistant-skills/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Zonaina Aguil Sampayan

Cor Jesu College, Inc. – Philippines